

Original Research Article

Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices Regarding Indecent Dressing among University of Lahore Students Affecting their Academic Performance

Shahmeen Shahbaz^{1*}, Muhammad Afzal², Muhammad Hussain³, Safa Ikram⁴, Arooj Younis⁵

Abstract

¹BS Nursing, Lahore School of Nursing, The University of Lahore, PO box 54000, Lahore, Pakistan

²Associate Professor, Lahore School of Nursing, the University of Lahore, PO box 54000, Lahore, Pakistan.

³Assistant Professor, Lahore School of Nursing, the University of Lahore, PO box 54000., Lahore, Pakistan.

⁴BS Nursing, Lahore School of Nursing, The University of Lahore, PO box 54000, Lahore, Pakistan.

⁵BS Nursing, Lahore School of Nursing, The University of Lahore, PO box 54000, Lahore, Pakistan.

*Corresponding Author E-mail:
shahmeenshabbaz@gmail.com

The objective of this study is to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of university students regarding indecent dressing among UOL, Lahore Pakistan. The design of this study was quantitative descriptive cross sectional to assess knowledge, attitude and practice of university students regarding indecent dressing among UOL, Lahore Pakistan. The Study was held in UOL, Lahore for 6 months. In this analysis, a quantitative descriptive cross-sectional design was used. The university students had a sample size of 150. The purpose of this study is to examine the awareness, attitude and experience of university students regarding indecent dressing among UOL, Lahore Pakistan. SPSS version 21 analyzed the results, mean and standard deviation was used to assess university student's awareness and attitude and practices on indecent dressing. The overall experience of university students regarding indecent dressing among UOL, Lahore Pakistan was positive and the attitude of the mean was less than experience and of the practice is negative. A conducted study helped to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices of university students regarding indecent dressing in university of Lahore. The results of study showed positive knowledge among university students regarding indecent dressing in UOL. They showed positive attitudes regarding awareness of indecent dressing. However, proper educational programs must be held in universities or other educational institutes, in order to provide a large access of knowledge related to indecent dressings and its impacts on academic field of students.

Keywords: Indecent dressing, students, Knowledge, Attitude, Practices

INTRODUCTION

Indecent look has come back to characterize the dress pattern of many students on the campuses of upper learning in Nigeria. There is hardly any higher establishment of learning in this country that is not long-faced with this loathsome problem. Students in these campuses of learning particularly the feminine ones dressed up temptingly leaving abundant to be desired. The ladies decision skirts that they wear are simply "one inch" longer than their pants. They struggle to seat after

putting on such dresses, cross gutters. Apart from the deficient and tightly fit nature of those dresses, they are once more transparent, revealing sure components of the body that needs to be hidden from the glare of people. In the case of male students, their pattern of dressing is different. It makes them to look dirty and extremely unattractive with unkempt hairs and dirty jeans having pockets of holes deliberately created round the knees and also the lower part of the trousers (Adeboye, 2012).

It is obvious that indecent dressing has gradually confiscated the dress pattern of scholars in higher establishments of learning in Ghana and institutes are not any exception. It is becoming like a virulent disease spreading quickly and therefore the earlier it is stopped, the better for our desperate and vulnerable youth. What then is indecent dressing? To answer this question, it will be imperative to grasp the meaning of good dressing. Good dressing may be explained as the commonly accepted way of dressing ensuring that the important elements of the human body is not exposed (Egwim, 2010).

Indecent dressing therefore is the improper and provocative way of dressing relative to the society or culture during which it is being perpetrated. This can be to mention that indecent dressing can't be properly outlined in isolation of the social norms or spiritual boundaries. What's indecent to you in say Gold Coast is good elsewhere. This brings to the fore the assertion of some faculty of thoughts that indecent dressing is especially because of "foreign culture." which means this manner of dressing is alien to the African nation culture and is thus an affront to our terribly existence and identity.

Egwim (2010), stated indecent dressing throughout an extra specific term as a result of the attitude of someone, male or female that dresses to showoff parts of the body admire the breasts, buttocks or even the underwear notably those of the ladies that need to be covered. The waist of their trousers lowered and mounted tightly at the center of the 2 bottom lobes to reveal their boxers (pants). And once they are walking, they drag their legs and one amongst their hands particularly, the left one, bloodletting their invisible pouch as if they'll fall to the bottom if not supported. several of them owing to however they dressed had at only once or the opposite become victims of rape, lured into prostitution, used for ritual purpose, unable to complete their education or coaching and additionally engaged in other adjunct social and ethical issues like cultism and lying to say these few. Although, there are not any universally acceptable manner or ways that of dressing, dresses are meant to serve some determinable purposes, country or region not with-standing (Ms Best, 2012).

In addition, there are people who believe that indecent dressing bothers most on morality thence they judge some non-secular meanings to it. they are speech communication "indecent dressing is any form of dressing that the almighty father (the creator of the universe) abhors." in line with Olori (2003), this way of dressing is provocative, improper and virtuously unacceptable. These dress patterns virtuously offensive and reveal the high rate of moral abjection at intervals the society of our time (Omede, J. & Odiba, P, 2000).

With of these explanations, one is currently clear regarding the sort of dressing that's thought of indecent within the African country context. Not on a daily basis

passes while not some criticism or the opposite by colleague students, visitors, lecturers, non-teaching workers or other persons about the provocative dressing of Ho tech students, above all the girls. They wear deficient skirts, solely about one in. longer than their pants to lectures and other social gatherings in and outdoors campus. Quite excluding the skimpy and tightly fitting nature of those dresses, their clear nature additionally helps in exposing their thighs and other important parts of their body for public view. This makes them realize problem in ascent machines, crossing a gutter and even bending all the way down to decide something (Olori, T 2003).

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to assess knowledge, attitude and practice among students of UOL regarding impact of indecent dressing on their academic goals.

Objective

To assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of university students regarding indecent dressing in UOL.

Research Questions

How to investigate the gap between the current knowledge and actual practices among students of UOL regarding impact of indecent dressing on their academic goals.

Significance of the study

This study helped to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding indecent dressing influence on academic performance among students of University of Lahore. Majority of university students are unaware of the impact of their indecent dress up on their academic activities. The study aims to leads an optimistic pathway for students to make them well informed and well concerned about the negative effects of the indecent or improper dressing in university.

Literature Review

A study was conducted in Volta Region, Ghana, West Africa by Gbadegbe Richard Selase* and Quashie Mawuli. This paper in this manner looked for to examine the impacts or impacts bareness or indecent dressing has on the scholastic execution of Ho Polytechnic understudies in Ghana. This was done by employing the

graphic (subjective) strategy of investigate to depict the relationship between factors. The research strategy utilized was a case consider utilizing understudies (203), educating (126) and non-teaching staff (21) of Ho Polytechnic as the available populace. Information were collected for the think about by the work of the survey technique in which 450 survey duplicates were managed to the available populace. This was combined with the member attentive approach where foul dressings were watched and recorded. A fundamental finding of the ponder is that approximately 60% of Ho Polytechnic understudies dress obscenely. And out of this, approximately 80% are females while 20% are guys. This consider advance uncovered that provocative dressing or foul dressing destructs the attention of both understudies and speakers amid.

Conventional dressing can be clarified as the correct way of dressing or the by and large acknowledged way of dressing without uncovering imperative parts of the human body. Concurring to Yahaya (2013) a better than average dressing, of course, is portion of human life, since it evokes regard and secures the person's respect. Better than average dressing by students draws in regard from teachers, watches, classmates and most altogether secures you from being the target of assault and disappointment.

Agreeing to Bua and Ogbaji (2014), investigate uncovers that these wrongful and inappropriate dressings of College of Instruction Katsina Ala understudies contains a tall propensity of affecting contrarily on their academic performance as the yield of male teachers most particularly can decrease when they concentrate on watching such provocative dressings amid addresses. Female understudies on the other hand spend so much money in buying such futile dresses rather than investing them on their scholarly work. Their indecent dressing moreover makes them patronize discotheques, night clubs, brothels and hotels where they can have fun at the cost of their considers. There's moreover the plausibility of a few male speakers or indeed female lecturers falling prey to such enticing dressings which may result in sexual favors between the lecturers on one hand and understudies on the other hand. This clearly will be a prevention to quality instruction; as such students will not be able to perform up to the desire of their prospective.

Uba (2006) states that within the past a long time, when men were men and ladies were easygoing, the basic essence of covering the female life structures was of grave significance. Ladies were glad to cover up themselves, but nowadays all that appear to have been cleared off the tidy of history. Wherever you turn, on the street, within the transport, within the campus, within the showcase places, there all shapes and sorts of breast rudely and embarrassingly gaze at everybody in locate. The way understudies on these campuses of learning particularly, the female ones, dress enticingly takes off much to be craved. What the young ladies call skirts that

they wear is fair "one inch" longer than their pants. When they put on such dresses, they struggle to sit down, discover trouble in climbing machines, cross canals as well as choose anything from the ground. Separated from the meager and tight-fitting nature of these dresses, they are once more transparent; revealing certain parts of the bodies that beneath ordinary dressing designs have to be properly covered up.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional study is designed to figure out assessing the knowledge attitude and practice of university students of UOL regarding indecent dressing.

Sample Size

The population of this study was selecting the university students of UOL regarding indecent dressing. The target population consists of 150 participants and all were university students of UOL.

Study Setting

This study was conducted in the University of Lahore (UOL).

Study Population

The students of UOL were selected for the study population

Sampling

Simple Random sampling was used in this study

Research Instrument

A well written structured and adopted questionnaire from the study was used for collecting the data from the participant. After taking informed consent, data were collected from university students of UOL.

Data Gathering Procedure

A formal written letter of permission to conduct the research. Also, an ethical approval was obtained from the author to use this questionnaire and the

questionnaire was distributed to university students of UOL.

Sample Size

Slovin's sampling will be used to find the sample size of the study population.

If the total population is 240

If N=population n= sample size E= margin of error

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + (N)(E)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{240}{1 + (240)(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{240}{1 + (240)(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{240}{1 + 0.6}$$

$$n = \frac{240}{1.6}$$

$$n = 150$$

Inclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria included all university students who were willing to participate in our research study and gave informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

Exclusion criteria included who were not willing to participate in our research study. This segment also excluded those who were absent at the time of data collection process

Data Collection Techniques

Assessing students of UOL for the purpose of identifying issues related to indecent dressing. Assessment including questionnaire, observations, focus groups, interviews.

Ethical Consideration

In this research ethical consideration was highly preferred. For this purpose, the permission was obtained from the ethical committee of the health care institution, before data collection. Permission was acquired by a written approval from the head of the department of Lahore school of nursing in the form of consent. Furthermore, informed written and verbal consent was taken before data collection from participants. Students were given the right of autonomy and nature. The purpose of the study was informed prior to the implementation of any action. The risk related to this study was discussed before. Participants were given the right to leave the study participation at any time. In this

case other participants were added for the accomplishment of data information. Participants were informed about the aims of the study and secrecy of the collected data was assured. A written consent was taken from respondents who were willing to participate in this study. All respondents were informed that their participation is highly appreciated and they can participate voluntarily. Participants were taken in confidence that all the collected information and records remained confidential.

RESULT AND DATA ANALYSIS

Results and data analysis were taken up through systematic and logical techniques (SPSS) after the accomplishment of the data collection process. Table 1-6

Profile of the Respondents

Demographic Data

Respondents were taken from the University of Lahore Table 1 show that the gender of university students was male (52.7%) and females (47.3%).

Data was collected from a total of 150 university students, majority n=89, age of 25 to 30 years (59.3%). Majority n=112 educational status was bachelors (74.7%). Majority n=139 agreed that indecent dressing is not appropriate according to my family values (92.7%). Majority n=110 agreed that indecent dressing is not appropriate according to my societal norms and values (73.3%). Majority n=98 agreed that indecent dressing is not appropriate according to my religious point of views and values (65.3%). Majority n=92 agreed that imitation of western dressing style can divert our youth toward indecent dressing (61.3%). Majority n=84 agreed that peer/social group /pressure can become the causes of indecent dressing trends (56%). Majority n=78 agreed that fashion in vogue and inspiration towards the media is a major factor of indecent dressing (62%). Majority n=80 strongly agreed that indecent dressing is an act of indiscipline (53.3%). Majority n=88 strongly agreed that indecent dressing constituted a bad character (54%). Majority n=81 strongly agreed that indecent dressing constituted an immoral act (58.7%). Majority n=74 strongly agreed that indecent dressing constitutes unlearned behavior (49.3%). Majority n=63 strongly agreed that indecent dressing constitutes a bad model (42%). Majority n=87 strongly agreed that poor parenting plays a key role in enhancing indecent dressing among youth (44.7%). Majority n=62 strongly agreed that pulling trousers to the buttock is included in indecent dressing (41.3%). Majority n=64 strongly agreed that Exposing breasts and chest is included in indecent dressing (42.7%). Majority n=64 strongly agreed that wearing short dresses that expose thigh and underwear is included in

Table 1. Demographic data

Gender of participants

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	79	52.7	52.7	52.7
Female	71	47.3	47.3	100
Total	150	100	100	

Table 2. Age of Participants

Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18 to 24 years	57	38	38	38
25 to 30 years	89	59.8	59.3	97.3
31 to 35 years	4	2.7	2.7	100
Total	150	100	100	

Table 3. Educational status of Participants

Educational Status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Bachelors	112	74.7	74.7	74.7
Masters	38	25.3	25.3	100
Total	150	100	100	

Table 4. Section II Knowledge of the university students regarding indecent dressing

S.No	Knowledge of the students	%
1	Indecent dressing is not appropriate according to my family values	59.3%
2	Indecent dressing is not appropriate according to my societal norms and values	74.7%
3	Indecent dressing is not appropriate according to my religious point of view	92.7%
4	Imitation of western dressing style can divert our youth towards indecent dressing	73.3%
5	Peer/social group can become the cause of indecent dressing	65.3%

Table 5. SECTION III Attitude of the university students regarding indecent dressing

Sr.No	Attitudes of students	%
1	Indecent dressing is constitute as bad model	49.3%
2	Poor parenting plays key role in enhancing indecent dressing among youth	42%
3	Fashion in vogue and inspiration towards media is major cause of indecent dressing	61.3%
4	Indecent dressing is an act of indiscipline	56%
5	Indecent dressing constitute bad character	62%
6	Indecent dressing is constitute immoral act	53.3%
7	Indecent dressing is constitute as unlearned behavior	58.7%

Table 6. SECTION IV Practices of the university students regarding indecent dressing

Sr.No	Practices of students	%
3	Pulling the trousers to the buttocks are included in indecent dressings	44.7%
4	Exposing of breast and chest are included in indecent dressings	41.3%
5	Wearing of short dresses that expose thigh and underwear are included in indecent dressings	42.7%
6	Wearing of torn and worn clothes are included in indecent dressings	48%
7	Wearing clothes that don't covering the body properly are included in indecent dressings	44.7%
8	Wearing clothes without dupattas/stallers are included in indecent dressings	49.3%

the indecent dressing (42.7%). Majority n=72 strongly agreed that wearing of torn or worn clothes is included in indecent dressing (48%). Majority n=67 strongly agreed that wearing clothes that don't cover the body properly is included in indecent dressing (44.7%). Majority n=74 strongly agreed that wearing dresses without dupattas are included in indecent dressing (49.3%).

DISCUSSION

Present study was conducted to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices of university students in Lahore, Pakistan. Several studies were conducted related to this topic but the current study showed different results and conclusion in past studies the knowledge of students in

university was at a lower score but in present study the knowledge score of university students is relatively higher and positive towards indecent dressing. Most participated university students were middle aged with bachelors as their educational status. A study was conducted in Volta Region, Ghana, West Africa by Gbadegbe Richard Selase* and Quashie Mawuli. This paper in this manner looked for to examine the impacts or impacts bareness or indecent dressing has on the scholastic execution of Ho Polytechnic understudies in Ghana. This was done by employing the graphic (subjective) strategy of investigation to depict the relationship between factors. The research strategy utilized was a case considering utilizing understudies (203), educating (126) and non-teaching staff (21) of Ho Polytechnic as the available populace. Information was collected for the think about by the work of the survey technique in which 450 survey duplicates were managed to the available populace. This was combined with the member attentive approach where foul dressings were watched and recorded. A fundamental finding of the ponder is that approximately 60% of Ho Polytechnic understudies dress obscenely. And out of this, approximately 80% are females while 20% are guys. This Consider advance uncovered that provocative dressing or foul dressing destructs the attention of both understudies and speakers amid.

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Limitation

Study was conducted during a short period of time. Data collected from university students of UOL measuring the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice among them.

CONCLUSION

A conducted study helped to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices of university students regarding indecent dressing in university students of Lahore. The results of study showed positive knowledge among university students regarding indecent dressing in university. The study provided comprehensive concepts illustrating the knowledge, attitude, and practices among students of UOL regarding impact of indecent dressing on their academic goals; it helped to design

and implement evidence-based interventions in order to achieve betterment in academic performance.

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